

Living Labs and Open Toolkit for the co-design of
accessible IT systems and tools

PROJECT

Living Labs and Open Toolkit for the co-design of accessible IT systems and tools

AGREEMENT NUMBER

LC-01624438/101018048

Report: The gender dimension in LIVE IT

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Document Filename	The gender dimension in LIVE IT
Nature Of Document	R
Number Of Pages	25
Work Package	All Work Packages
Partner Responsible	All partners
Author(s)	All partners
Contributor(s)	All partners
Reviewed by	Joe Cullen
Approved by	Panagiotis Bamidis, Project Coordinator

PROJECT FULL TITLE	Living Labs and Open Toolkit for the co-design of accessible IT systems and tools
Start Of Project	1 April 2021
Duration	12 months
Project URL	https://liveit-project.eu/
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Acknowledgements

The LIVE IT team would like to thank all of our collaborating partners, especially those organisations working with us on the ground in developing the Co-Labs, and all of the LIVE IT ‘users’ – people with cognitive disabilities – for giving their time and insights to contribute to this research.

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1. Introduction

This document is an additional output from the LIVE IT project. The document focuses on the 'gender dimension' in LIVE IT. It sets out how the project approached the issue of gender in its objectives and activities; what actions were taken to explore how gender shapes the digital life of people with cognitive disabilities; whether gender is associated with the use of particular tools to support web accessibility and whether there are differences in outcomes associated with the use of these tools according to gender. It presents the key conclusions of the work on gender and their implications going forward.

Positioning the gender dimension in LIVE IT

LIVE IT made a commitment in its project implementation plan to explore the gender dimension in two main ways:

- To deepen understandings of the role sex and gender plays in the relationship between cognitive impairment and digital inclusion (through the state-of-the-art review and lifeworld analysis)
- To embed a gender dimension in the development of tools to support inclusive web accessibility in the Labs and in the production of the Open Toolkit and meta-environment.

The first objective was addressed as follows:

- Establishing an overview of the broad picture of gender, cognitive disability and web accessibility through a limited 'realist review' of the literature, looking for key themes
- Drilling down further into the literature to map the landscape of inclusive web accessibility, focusing on the perspective of people with cognitive disabilities. This was done through a systematic review of the literature in three academic databases: SCOPUS, ProQuest, and Web of Science, using rapid evidence assessment methods.
- Supplementing the literature review with an 'interventions review'. This interventions audit collected, collated and analysed examples of good practices – 'interventions'- including examples of platforms and tools - that have the potential to support inclusive web accessibility. It was carried out using 'scientific realist review'.
- Documenting and understanding how the digital world operates within the lived experience and daily lives of people with cognitive disabilities by carrying out 'lifeworld analysis' research combining 7 Focus Groups involving 60 people and 52 face to face interviews with people with cognitive disabilities and their carers. The focus groups and interviews were supplemented by observation analysis involving 38 people with cognitive disabilities and content analysis of 68 key documents.

The second objective was addressed by:

- Promoting equal gender representation in project activities, including the 'lifeworld analysis, Co-Lab activities and the Hackathons
- Documenting and assessing the extent to which variations in the use of tools within the Co-Labs and Hackathons – and the outcomes associated with the use of tools – can be linked to gender.

The following sections of this document report on the above work:

- First, we provide a brief overview of the main themes highlighted in the general literature review
- This is followed by the key findings of the focused systematic review, the interventions audit and the lifeworld analysis
- The next section of the document assesses gender representation in the LIVE IT project
- The following section explores gender variations in the use of tools to support web accessibility
- The concluding section presents the main conclusions on the gender dimension together with their implications going forward.

Overview: gender, cognitive disability and digital life

The gender dimension of cognitive disability and web accessibility is complex. One common strand in the literature is an acknowledgement that there does appear to be a link between gender and patterns of disability, their underlying causes and their associated impacts. However, this link is both contested and lacks an established evidence base. On the one hand, it is fairly well-accepted that the incidence of cognitive disability across a range of presenting disorders is associated with gender. For example, a consistent pattern in the epidemiology of Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is the higher prevalence in males compared to females, with ASD diagnosed four times more often in males than in females, although this rate has been found to vary across different studies (Maenner et. al., 2020; Napolitano et. al., 2021).

More contested and less well-established is the evidence that tries to establish the causal pathways between gender and cognitive disability. For example, gender is associated with increased risk of developing dementia in several European cohort studies, which seems to be linked to lifestyle factors such as occupation, exercise and diet (Gilsanz et. al., 2017). Similarly, the evidence suggests that, although boys are more likely to present with ADHD than girls, females presenting with ADHD are more likely to present with co-morbidity issues, and to continue presenting these into adulthood- for example through depression, anxiety, unhealthy lifestyles (Hasson and Fine, 2012). What seems to be a recurrent theme in these studies is that combinations of biological, social and cultural factors serve to shape the relationship between gender and cognitive disability, and subsequently its effects (Au et. al, 2107). For example, a study in China showed that mild cognitive disability in men was associated with a history of smoking and hypertension, and for women with a history of illiteracy and farm labour occupations (Liu et. al. 2022). Similarly, a study in Japan, looking particularly at the ‘health-survival paradox’ – why women live longer but tend to suffer more debilitations and illness – found that gender differences in cognitive functioning and decline underpin different individual attributes of cognitive disability and their social determinants. In particular, men seem to be more engaged in activities which accumulate intellectual experiences through education and occupation, and this subsequently shapes patterns of cognitive disability and its impacts (Okamoto et. al., 2021).

These combinations of biological, social and cultural factors are not well-understood, and they raise important questions that go beyond mapping the incidence of cognitive disability against socio-demographic and socio-cultural constructs. For example, some research suggests that the social construction of cognitive disability is an important factor in reinforcing gender differences, like in the way teachers treat girls presenting with ADHD differently from how they treat boys (Diamantopoulou et. al., 2007). Moreover, as

Thompson, Caruso and Ellerbeck (2003) point out, not only do the research data suggest there may be significant differences in the presentation of some developmental disabilities (both strengths and weaknesses) between females and males in cognitive, behavioral, mental health and pathophysiological domains, but cultural differences in the way males and females with developmental disabilities are treated may have an impact on diagnosis as well as interventions provided. This raises important questions regarding the adequacy of services for females with cognitive disabilities.

This brings into play the distinction between 'sex' and 'gender' in the context of cognitive disability and digital life. In line with WHO and most national guidelines, we define sex as 'the biological aspects of an individual', and something assigned at birth, and 'gender' as 'a social construction relating to behaviours and attributes based on labels of masculinity and femininity', which speaks to the concept of 'gender identity' and the internal perception of their gender someone identifies with (UK Office for National Statistics [Link](#)). As Barnes (2022) observes "Identity-based views of gender categorization put a cognitive requirement on gender membership... identifying as gender x, is a matter of complex social reasoning and self-understanding. But many cognitively disabled people have little or no access to language. Many tend not to understand social norms, much less to identify those norms as specifically gendered". She points to 'a substantial body of research (which) suggests that there are striking gender differences in the treatment of cognitively disabled people' including the increased risk of sexual abuse, inappropriate medical treatment and endemic disempowerment (McCarthy, 1998). These issues are amplified if we move beyond the narrow binary construction of gender. One study in the US found that adults who identify as transgender or gender non-binary more often reported worsening memory and thinking, functional limitations and depression than cisgender adults. This, it is suggested, may be due in part to anti-transgender stigma and prejudice that expose transgender people to high rates of mistreatment and discrimination where they live, work, learn, seek health care and age (Cicero E, et al 2021). A separate study found that transgender and gender non-binary adults had significantly higher reports of cognitive disability compared with cisgender adults (Lambrou et. al., 2019).

In relation to digital inclusion, the evidence is clearer, with women much less likely to have access to a smartphone or the internet; much less likely to hold a post in digital and media industries; score lower on average in digital and media competences and have less confidence in their ability to use digital tools (OECD, 2018). These gender differences are again exacerbated by factors such as level of education, social and cultural background and economic status (Cullen, et. al., 2015; 2020). As with the relationship between gender and cognitive disability, gender is mediated through the digital world in complex ways. We know that gender inequalities reinforce digital inequalities and vice versa – an illustration of what has been called 'dual exclusion' (Helsper and van Duersen, 2015) – and that gender influences access to information – which is fundamental to social and political participation. Decreased social and political participation as a result of gender discrimination in turn reinforces the reproduction of inequalities. In addition, females tend to be less confident and more anxious than males about IT use, reducing their sense of digital self-efficacy and increasing perceptions of IT requiring greater effort (Goswami and Dutta, 2015).

Some commentators have argued that gender divisions on the web are responsible for creating 'regressive and destructive forms of social bonds' which, amplified by the globalization of cyberspace, lead to exaggerated forms of individualism, which further

accentuates gender inequalities in cyberspace (Toto and Scarinisci, 2021). As more and more of the services that govern day to day existence have moved online as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, existing gender inequalities on access, ownership of digital devices, digital and media literacy and the capacity to make meaningful use of access to technology have significantly widened (Mariscal et. al., 2019). For example, a recent study on the use of online healthcare services concluded that there is a risk of digital exclusion among those females who are socio-economically disadvantaged, in poor health, or socially isolated, and that this may predispose people with high needs for health services to exclusion from them (Heponiemi et. al., 2020).

Research on the relationship between cognitive disability, gender and the use of digital and media technologies is very hard to come by. The general literature review strongly suggests that these aspects tend to be approached separately, rather than as interconnected phenomena. So, for example, one strand in the literature on gender and the digital world focuses on the norms and values that shape how user interfaces are designed. This mainly covers how tools and content are heavily gendered – for example the use of stereotypical male/female characters and their appearance and clothing in online games; the use of gender targeted advertising in social media and the use of gendered fields in online forms (See for example [Link](#)). This is mirrored by literature and research on how disability is approached on the web. A significant amount of the literature focuses on ways of supporting web accessibility, a good example being the principles and Guidelines produced by W3C ([Link](#)). Although there is an extensive body of literature on the stereotyping of people with disabilities in the media in general there is very little literature that specifically covers how disabled people are portrayed through digital and online content. As a recent report on research in online gaming carried out by 'Scope' observes, there is little published research that explores the experiences of disabled gamers. The research carried out by Scope revealed that around two thirds of gamers with a disability who took part in the research reported barriers to their gaming – the most significant being the affordability of assistive or adaptive technology. The research also suggested that disabled gamers are more engaged than non-disabled gamers across key platforms and touchpoints ([Link](#)).

One of the few strands in research literature we identified that tries to join the dots between gender, cognitive disability and digital life suggests that some digital tools may be more effective in supporting people with cognitive disability depending on their gender, and on the presenting cognitive issue. For example, one study on the use of 'Smart Sound' training software to support cognitive rehabilitation in reading disorder found that cognitive rehabilitation increases the working memory capacity of students with special learning disabilities (reading) among girls more than boys (Raziyeh, Turaj and Akbar, 2021). In contrast, another study, which examined whether the use of ICTs improves the writing performance of students with ADHD as well as the impact of gender, revealed that the boys who used ICTs outperformed the boys who did not. However, there was no qualitative difference in the girl's performance, regardless of whether they used or did not use ICTs. The study concluded that attitude and self-belief had a key impact on the use of ICT tools, and the outcomes of that use (Andreou, Riga & Papayiannis, 2016). Since, as noted above, gender is a significant determinant of attitude and self-belief, it follows that it is likely to play an important role in the efficacy and effectiveness of tools to support web accessibility.

A broader strand of work that has tried to get a purchase on the complex inter-relationships between cognitive disability, gender and digital life draws on an intersectional perspective.

This aims to expose the interlocking systems that define the lives of excluded and marginalised people (Crenshaw, 1989). It considers people's overlapping identities and experiences in order to understand the complexity of the discrimination and inequalities they face – for example the amplification of domestic violence through gender and disability status (Bhadra, 2019). With regard to digital inclusion, as noted above, it's been known for some time that gender in combination with NEET status (not in education, employment or training) constrains access to and usage of digital technologies, which in turn exacerbates socio-economic disadvantage (Passey et. al., 2008). This is compounded by cultural factors that are embedded in the 'masculine' engineering of technology and in power structures that make it difficult for females to occupy positions of authority in the digital world (Cranmer, 2006; Helsper, 2010; ITU, 2012; Oudshoorn et. al., 2016).

Other research has considered how digital life is experienced through the 'entanglement' of immigration status and low income (Hallbeg et. al., 2016; Powell, 2010). A recent study of the digital life of low-income women in Amsterdam showed that engagement in the digital world was mainly influenced by motherhood, poverty and the perceived complexities of ICTs – all of which were amplified through being first-generation, non-Western immigrants (Goetard et. al., 2019).

Applying concepts and insights from intersectionality suggests that females and those people with cognitive disabilities who identify as non-binary occupy complex, intersectional spaces in multiple, interlocking communities that reflect highly contextualised access to and potential utilisation of economic, social and cultural capitals – including digital technologies and services. It seems probable that the way these tools and services are currently designed, configured and delivered reflects a gendered disconnect with the lifeworlds and lived experience of people with cognitive disabilities. This is further explored below.

2. Key findings from LIVE IT's preliminary research

Findings from the focused review and interventions audit

The key findings of the focused systematic review we carried out on web accessibility for people with cognitive disability reinforce the conclusions of the general literature review reported on in the previous section. This review entailed a comprehensive content analysis of key policies and guidelines on web accessibility, together with 45 examples of research studies drawn from an initial search of bibliographic databases. The key policies and guidelines analysed include the United Nations (UN) Convention on Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) - the overarching policy that both informs and drives the EU and individual state policies - as well as the World Wide Web Consortium's (W3C's) Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) which serve as a foundation for EU and individual state policies. These over-arching policies and guidelines were criticised for their lack of accessibility specifications to support people with cognitive disabilities, and, in response, WC3 developed the COGA Task Force, whose mission is to improve current accessibility standards and recommend new accessibility standards focused on people with cognitive disabilities.

However, although this development suggests that the cognitive angle is now being taken more seriously in relation to web accessibility in these and other major global policy initiatives, we found little evidence of policies and guidelines linking cognitive disability to gender within the context of web accessibility. For example, the WCAG contains no specific reference to the gender dimension of web accessibility. To take another example, the

United Nations Entity for Gender Equality and the Empowerment of Women (UNWomen) has produced a 'Gender Accessibility Audit Toolkit' to support increased web accessibility for females, aimed at policymakers, practitioners and disability rights advocates. The Toolkit reflects the recognition that gender acts as a powerful reinforcer of other barriers that militate against participation: "These barriers create multiple and intersecting forms of discrimination against women and girls with disabilities, in particular, with regard to equal access to education, economic opportunities, social interaction and justice, equal recognition before the law, and the ability to participate in politics and exercise control over their own lives" (UNWomen, 2018). The Toolkit covers the spectrum of disabilities but has no specific focus on cognitive disability. In addition, although it states that accessibility audits can and should be implemented in sectors like IT services, a lot of the ground covered relates to physical communication barriers and accessibility issues – such as transport systems and building design.

Similarly, our analysis of the research studies carried out in the focused review revealed no studies specifically focused on the role of gender. This finding was reinforced by the audit carried out of over 300 tools and other interventions, for example guidelines, developed to support increased web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities. We found no examples targeted specifically at females or non-binary groups.

Findings from the lifeworld analysis

As noted above, with regard to digital inclusion, research shows that gender in combination with poverty constrains access to and usage of digital technologies, which in turn exacerbates socio-economic disadvantage. This is compounded by cultural factors that are embedded in the 'masculine' engineering of technology and in power structures that make it difficult for females to occupy positions of authority in the digital world. Other research has considered how digital life is experienced through the 'entanglement' of immigration status and low income. Our LWA research for LIVE IT lends support to this research and its attempt to trace the intersections between gender, disability and socio-economic inequalities. Particularly in the South London, Bristol and Portuguese research sites, we found evidence of cognitive disability intersecting with low income, gender and cultural background to engender 'first order' obstacles to digital engagement – i.e. lack of digital access. For example, one female who participated in the UK lifeworld analysis research reported that her 'whole life has been shaped by her learning disabilities, gender, immigrant status, and poverty'. She is the only female in a 'difficult family' and the family relies on her for economic and other forms of support. She felt that 'the system is against her' – for example in terms of her ability to access an apartment of her own as well as accessing the digital tools and services that would improve her life.

According to the 'multiple access' model (Helsper and van Deursen, 2015), first order barriers lead in turn to the 'second order' digital divide, which focuses on barriers to usage capability - the acquisition of digital competences so people are able to use digital devices efficiently and effectively - and 'quality of use' – whether digital services are designed to meet the needs of vulnerable people. Through our LWA research we found evidence to support this long-established argument that social inequalities – driven in this case through disability and associated intersectionalities like gender and cultural background – influence the acquisition of digital competences. In Portugal, for example, several female LWA participants reported they had little or no digital skills, and welcomed the opportunity to acquire them through the education and training provided in LIVE IT. Equally the LWA

highlighted evidence to suggest that digital services are not configured to the needs and situations of people with cognitive disabilities, as illustrated by the experiences of the mainly female students in Ireland who referred to the dominance of ‘ableist’ thinking in digital service design and delivery and their feelings of being ‘digitally invisible’. It was suggested that girls and women with cognitive disabilities tend to have lower confidence and skills in using digital tools and have usually received less input and support at school. This then lays the foundations for continual disengagement through subsequent life with anything digital. One participant reported that her – now deceased – partner had taken responsibility for everything digital in their home. She could not use a smartphone, PC or tablet without significant help and was now effectively excluded from the web.

A key theme emerging from the LWA, framed through the prism of gender, was that female digital needs are not taken seriously. Several women who participated in the research reported they had to fight to get a diagnosis of cognitive disability formally recognised. Their requests for support were seen as ‘shrill or whiney’. This meant they had to cope for many years on their own, leading to additional trauma associated with ‘being ignored’ added to the trauma of their disability. This seems to be particularly problematic in the case of women perceived as ‘high achievers’ who – because of their perceived capability – were often categorised as not needing help. As one participant in the LWA carried out in Ireland observed:

“And I, I also think in that case, being a woman, and being, having to be persistent because of my condition, which I'm sure there are many who have it, as well. But being a woman, I feel it's a different...If I say a different tone on it, or a different colour, do you know what I meant? Yea. I'm sure there's a nice English or scientific word for it, I just can't remember at the moment because I use phrases like tone and colour”.

One important repercussion of this process in the context of web accessibility is that it lays the foundations for a ‘self-defeating behaviour cycle’. One female participant in the LWA research reported she had ‘developed an approach that masked her vulnerability and needs’. This reinforced a resistance to asking for help, denial in terms of digital needs and avoidance of online services. Another participant reported a similar pattern. She denies having a disability in public, she can't read and has such difficulty with logging on that jigsaw games and YouTube music videos (if she is helped to log-on) are the only services she can use.

Following the ‘second order’ divide, the multiple access model introduces a ‘third order’ dimension, which considers the consequences of digital technologies and their relationship to economic, social, civic and cultural wellbeing. The third-level digital divide focuses mainly on disparities in the returns from internet use within populations of users who exhibit broadly similar usage profiles and enjoy relatively autonomous and unfettered access to ICTs and the internet infrastructure. Third-level divides, therefore, relate to gaps in individuals’ capacity to translate their internet access and use into favorable offline outcomes. Although the factors that determine these offline outcomes are complex and sometimes contradictory – for example research by Van Deursen and Helsper suggests that unemployed men use the internet more and extract more benefit from it than employed men, probably because they have more free time – there appears to be a broad relationship between higher social status and the offline advantages extracted from digital engagement (Van Deursen and Helsper, 2015). Our LWA research suggests that cognitive disability is a

strong intersectional factor that interacts with socio-economic status and other factors to shape digital engagement – which means that female people with cognitive disabilities are then more likely to lose out in converting their digital assets into offline assets. For example, one older woman who participated in the LWA found it really difficult admitting need and asking for help. She can't read; has difficulty understanding or answering questions and has difficulty navigating online forms with complex fields. As a result, she was unable to apply for her pension online.

However, the LWA research suggests that different dynamics play out differently in different settings. For example, whilst the research identified the common perception of 'digital invisibility' across the range of research sites covered, and what Habermas has called 'the separation of lifeworld from system' (Habermas, 1984) the research also found evidence of social inclusion being supported when the community opens up spaces for authentic engagement with digital tools in the context of everyday life. One illustration of this is the 'ecological' emergence in the community of digital support networks that provide help and support for people with disabilities. In this context, connectivity challenges, like lack of access to high speed broadband, and usage capability challenges, like limited digital skills training opportunities, can be compensated for by resources and assets sourced from the intersectional communities people with disabilities are engaged with, though, for example, non-disabled females living in the same housing block sharing digital devices with disabled females when needed, and families and peer groups helping each other to acquire digital skills through learning by doing.

3. Gender representation in the LIVE IT project

People with cognitive disabilities were involved in a range of LIVE IT activities as follows:

- preliminary work carried out through baseline research, which entailed carrying out 'lifeworld analysis' research to document and understand how the digital world operates within the lived experience and daily lives of people with cognitive disabilities
- intensive work with participants in the LIVE IT Co-Labs, leading to the mapping and analysis of challenges that prevent people with cognitive disabilities fully benefiting from digital life. These challenges were mapped against 1200 tools with the potential to deliver solutions to these challenges
- subsequent co-creation work carried out in the Co-Labs, involving people with cognitive disabilities as co-designers and co-developers exploring the efficacy of a range of these tools
- five Hackathons implemented over the project lifecycle which carried out further experiments with the suite of assistive tools, and with the LIVE IT 'Open Toolkit', to deliver recommendations for changes to assistive tools, ideas for new tools and improvements to the Open Toolkit.

As noted above the lifeworld analysis research work involved 112 individuals, the majority presenting with cognitive disabilities and the remainder involving carers. There was an overall roughly equal split between males and females, but there were variations in the gender balance between the four countries involved in the research, with significantly more females (75%) represented in Greece (75%) and Ireland (84%).

Figure 1 shows the gender distribution of the 355 people who took part in the LIVE IT Co-Lab activities and the 200 people who took part in the LIVE IT Hackathons combined. There was

no significant difference in gender distribution between the Co-Lab activities and the Hackathons.

Figure 1: Gender distribution of participants in LIVE IT Co-Labs and Hackathons

As Figure 1 shows, overall, the gender distribution was slightly skewed towards females, with 57%, and 43% identifying as male. This distribution was reversed for Greece. In the UK and Ireland, around 60% of participants identified as female. In Portugal, 69% of participants identified as male.

4. Gender variations in use of tools and their associated outcomes

People with cognitive disabilities participated in 354 experiments with tools to increase web accessibility in the LIVE IT Co-Labs, involving 72 different ‘scenarios of use’ of the tools, aimed at identifying solutions to digital challenges – for example signing in or completing authentication processes. 200 participants were also involved in exploring the use of tools – and the usefulness of the LIVE IT ‘Open Toolkit’ – in the Hackathons. These activities and experiments were documented and evaluated using observation, interviews, user surveys and screen capture. In addition, two focused experiments were carried out in the Greece Co-Lab to specifically explore the role of gender in tool use and outcomes.

Survey findings

The surveys used an adapted version of the item System Usability Scale (Brooke, 1986). There are three scales to measure tool usability and usefulness (extent to which the tool/app meets user needs; ease of use of the tool/app; capacity of the tool/app to deliver the tasks required) and four ‘semantic differential’ scales to measure the user’s ‘emotional response’ (overwhelmed-in control; distracted-focused; frustrated-encouraged; stressed-relaxed). Supplementary open-ended questions capture user perceptions of the challenges encountered using the tools; the things that worked well and the improvements needed.

The survey results were analysed to explore whether variations in the rating attributed to the tools used in the Co-labs and Hackathons could be linked to gender. Figure 2 shows the

combined aggregated mean ratings of participants on the tools used, as measured by the seven usability, usefulness and emotional response scales.

Figure 2: Tool ratings by gender

As Figure 2 shows, the data show only small differences in aggregate ratings for the tools according to the gender participants' identified with. A student's t-test found no statistically significant differences in ratings across all seven measures between male and female participants.

Figure 3 shows the mean aggregate scores for tool Usability – combining participant ratings on user needs, ease of use and capacity to support task completion – and tool Emotional Response – combining participant ratings on the 'overwhelmed-in control'; 'distracted-focused'; 'frustrated-encouraged' and 'stressed-relaxed' semantic scales – broken down by participant gender identification.

Figure3: Mean aggregate scores on tool Usability and Emotional Response by gender

Figure 3 shows:

- Female participants rated tool usability slightly higher – a mean of 10.5 – than male participants – a mean of 10.4.
- Male participants rated tool Emotional Response higher – a mean of 19.4 - than female participants – a mean of 18.1.
- A students t-test showed these differences were not statistically significant.

However, although the overall picture on user ratings of the tools explored in the LIVE IT experiments and Hackathons showed no significant differences in terms of gender, some significant differences were identified across the different locations in which these activities were carried out. Figure 4 shows the mean aggregate Usability scores by gender and country location.

Figure 4: Mean aggregate Usability scores by gender and country location

As Figure 4 shows, across all four country locations, the differences in mean usability scores in terms of participant gender identification were negligible.

However, this is not the case for Emotional Response, as Figure 5 shows.

Figure 5: Mean aggregate Emotional Response scores by gender and country location

As Figure 5 shows, participants in Portugal who identified as male gave a higher rating on average on Emotional Response to the tools used – 20.7 – than those who identified as female – 17.8 – a statistically significant difference as measured by a students' t-test ($p=0.049$). Similarly, in the UK, participants who identified as male gave a higher rating on average on Emotional Response to the tools used – 18.8 – than those who identified as female – 15.5 – although this difference was not statistically significant. There is no clear explanation for these identified differences. The main reason for this is that the survey sample sizes are too small to cross-tabulate gender against location against presenting cognitive disability against type of tool used with any degree of confidence.

Findings from the observation, focus groups and interviews

Analysis of the qualitative data derived from user observation, focus groups and interviews doesn't provide much additional illumination of the gender dimension in tool use and its outcomes. We found no clear observable patterns of user-tool interaction and behaviour associated with gender across the activities recorded. On the one hand, observational analysis tends to reinforce the picture highlighted above in the discussion of the results of the LIVE IT lifeworld analysis that females are more likely to come into the LIVE IT Co-Labs and the Hackathons with less digital skills and less confidence than male participants. For example, in one of the UK locations it was observed that females were more apprehensive about what they were letting themselves in for. This attitude was reinforced by the wider skills range – and greater level of confidence – displayed by their male colleagues. However, it was also observed that – in the same location – females were 'hungrier for help and excited about the possibility of help that they'd never received before'. We also found no hard evidence through observation that females used tools in different ways, or that there were different outcomes associated with the use of these tools. The over-riding theme drawn from the observation is that all participants presented with highly variable and specific complex needs. These needs were not obviously mediated through gender – in the sense that females clearly showed a preference for particular tools and gained more benefit from using those tools, and vice versa. However, it seems clear that females brought a particular set of psycho-social and socio-cultural attributes into the LIVE IT activities – centred around factors like previous digital experience, sense of self-efficacy and confidence, as well as particular levels of digital and media competences and that these attributes shaped their subsequent digital behaviours and perceptions of outcomes.

These findings were reinforced by the data drawn from interviews and focus groups. When asked to specify the main challenges encountered using a specific tool or app, respondents gave a range of answers that were not clustered according to participant gender identification. Equally we found no evidence that participants attributed particular challenges encountered to gender characteristics. The same conclusions hold for responses to the questions 'What things worked well about the tool/app?' and 'How could you improve this tool/app?'.

Findings from the gender focused experiments

In order to further explore more systematically the role of gender in tool use and outcomes two focused experiments were carried out in the Greece Co-Lab to specifically explore the role of gender in tool use and outcomes through co-creation activities. The activities presented some real-life scenarios, involving particular web accessibility challenges, and then asked participants to develop the scenarios with suggested ICT tools. There was no

time or other limitation attached to the activity and the procedure was completed with respect to participants' diagnosis and individual preferences and need.

The first experiment involved 10 students with intellectual disability and autism spectrum disorder. Eight students (4 male, 4 female) between 15-20 years old with moderate/severe intellectual disability and 2 students (male), 15 years old with autism spectrum disorder (one with moderate intellectual disability comorbidity) participated. All students had a similar background regarding the use of technology, as measured by self-reported digital competence level, and verified by participating staff (neuropsychologists and sociologists). Participants were presented with the scenarios of interest and the tools selected to explore solutions to them. Participant tool use and outcomes were documented using a structured observation guideline and activity follow-up questionnaire.

Analysis of the data revealed some differences in the use and perceived outcomes of the tools used according to gender. The key findings were as follows. Male students (4) with severe intellectual disability tended to show more excitement about using the tools and displayed more confidence in using the speech-to-text (S2T) converters than the female participants (4) with similar diagnosis. In addition, female participants seemed to pay more attention to using tools like ContrastChecker, Coloradd-color identification and Visual Keyboard, which were tools that required minimum effort by the female participants. One explanation of this finding could be that S2T ICT tools offered a quick positive reinforcement to male participants, which fulfilled their needs of self-efficacy and subjective competence. On the other hand, female participants did not appear to be animated or excited about the reinforcement and voice feedback provided to their commands; females seemed more animated about the color functionalities afforded by different ICT tools (e.g., google chrome, Coloradd-color identification, ContrastChecker). They also appeared more responsive to the human interaction provided in the activity (e.g., psychologists who explained the use of an ICT tool) rather than the 'technological' aspects of the tools themselves. Finally, both male participants with moderate severe disability and autism spectrum disorder appeared to use S2T tools and Google Chrome with efficacy and showed strong interest in continuing the scenario (role playing with ICT tools).

In the second experiment five (5) people with ADHD, aged between 30-50 years old, participated in a co-creation session in the Lab of Medical Physics and Digital Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki. All participants had good knowledge of technology and experience in technological tools as laptops/desktops/smartphones (moderate to very good, as self-reported and verified by attending neuropsychologists). As with the first experiment participants were presented with the scenarios of interest and the tools selected to explore solutions to them. Participant tool use and outcomes were documented using a structured observation guideline and activity follow-up questionnaire.

Analysis of the data revealed some differences in the use and perceived outcomes of the tools used according to gender. Male participants with ADHD were more animated and excited about tools like Grammarly. In contrast, though they appreciated the functional utility of Grammarly, female participants preferred S2T tools and converters, like NVDA, textfromtoSpeech, Microsoft Speech to text converter, Microsoft Word Dictation and Read-Aloud. Male participants reported they were unlikely to use these S2R tools outside the Co-Lab environment. One explanation for this is that their use would undermine male participants' need to appear competent and in control – especially, for example, in a work setting. This explanation is supported by the finding that male participants showed greater

preference for ICT tools like Minimal Consent, Cookie Notice Blocker, as well as the LIVE IT Open Toolkit itself, which were seen as practical. In contrast, female participants were unenthusiastic about using Blockers but valued digital organisers like Google Calendar, Microsoft To Do List and Microsoft Whiteboard. It's important not to read too much into these findings – particularly given the small population involved. However, they do support the findings from the survey, observational, focus group and interview data, as well as the results of the first focused gender experiment reported above in that user behaviours seem to reflect psycho-social and socio-cultural differences that are mediated through gender. Males in this second experiment seem to prefer tools that reinforce their sense of self-efficacy and competence – for example valuing Grammarly as a way of correcting their mistakes, thereby amplifying these self-perceptions. Females gravitated more to S2T converters, which appeared to instil for them a sense of being guided, supported and looked after. Equally they valued organising and planning tools that appeared to contribute to creating an ordered and manageable environment, one that is perhaps seen as an antidote to a lived experience that is often challenging and sometimes scary.

5. Conclusions and implications

Key conclusions

The key conclusions of LIVE ITs work on the gender dimension are as follows.

- Our over-arching review of the literature highlighted the complexity of the relationship between gender, cognitive disability and digital accessibility. On the one hand there is an evidence base that links gender to patterns of cognitive disability – as evidenced by studies that show Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) has a higher prevalence in males compared to females. Similarly, there is some evidence that females are more likely to present with co-morbidity issues – for example females presenting with ADHD are more likely to experience issues throughout life associated with lower life opportunities. Equally there is an established evidence base that shows females are more likely to experience 'dual exclusion' – less access to digital tools and services and the training needed to use them effectively, leading to reduced digital and media competences and a lower 'quality of digital life', which in turn exacerbates economic and social vulnerability.
- However, there is very little compelling evidence on the relationship between cognitive disability, gender and the use of digital and media technologies. Some studies suggest that some digital tools may be more effective in supporting people with cognitive disability depending on their gender, and on the presenting cognitive issue. But the evidence is patchy and sometimes contradictory. More broadly, research on 'intersectionality' – which aims to explore the interlocking systems that define the lives of excluded and marginalised people, and particularly the role of gender in these interlocking systems – suggests that digital life is mediated through sex and gender and the ways in which these two factors are 'entangled' with factors like ethnicity, economic situation and lifeworld. Females and people with cognitive disabilities who identify as non-binary occupy complex, intersectional spaces in multiple, interlocking communities that in many ways are disconnected from 'mainstream' digital life.
- The findings from LIVE IT's 'baseline' research – which included a a focused systematic review on web accessibility for people with cognitive disability, an

‘interventions audit’ of tools and other interventions aimed at supporting people with cognitive disabilities, together with a detailed exploration of how digital life is experienced through everyday life – carried out using ‘lifeworld analysis’ – reinforce the picture painted in our general literature review of a field that is complex, contradictory and lacking an established evidence base. We found no examples of policies, guidelines or tools that specifically focused on gender. However, the results of the lifeworld analysis reinforce the impression drawn from the literature that ‘intersectionality’ defines the digital life of female and non-binary people with cognitive disabilities. A persistent narrative identified in the lifeworld analysis told the story of women whose cognitive disability was mis-diagnosed or not taken seriously in early life; who subsequently experienced feelings of inadequacy and low self-confidence; whose life opportunities – including access to digital tools and training – were significantly constrained and who ultimately end up excluded from the digital world.

- Turning to the subject of gender representation in LIVE IT, the upwards of 500 people who took part in the project activities – including lifeworld analysis, the experiments carried out in the project ‘Co-Labs’ and in the series of Hackathons implemented - show a broadly equal split between males and females, although some variations in gender balance were identified between the four participating countries. It is worth noting that no participant involved identified as non-binary.
- In our evaluation of these project activities, we looked at the role of gender and in particular whether variations in the use of tools within the Co-Labs and Hackathons – and the outcomes associated with the use of tools – can be linked to gender. This was done through observation, including screen capture, interviews, user surveys and focus groups, as well as two focused experiments carried out in the Greece Co-Lab to specifically explore the role of gender in tool use and outcomes.
- The results of the user surveys revealed very little difference overall in how participants rated digital tools to support web accessibility on the key measures of ‘usability’ and ‘emotional response’ according to gender, although, in Portugal, males gave a higher mean aggregate rating on the combined tools used in the experiments on ‘emotional response’ than females – a statistically significant difference.
- Analysis of the qualitative data derived from user observation, focus groups and interviews did not provide much additional illumination of the gender dimension in tool use and its outcomes. We found no clear observable patterns of user-tool interaction and behaviour associated with gender across the activities recorded. However, the data analysis did reinforce the picture highlighted by the LIVE IT lifeworld analysis that females are more likely to come into the LIVE IT Co-Labs and the Hackathons with less digital skills and less confidence than male participants. This did influence to some degree their expectations about using the tools in the experiments, their selection of particular tools and their evaluation of those tools.
- This observation is supported by the results of the two focused experiments carried out in the Greece Co-Lab. We found that males showed a preference for and were more likely to positively evaluate tools that reinforced their sense of self-efficacy, control and competence. In contrast, females showed a preference for and valued

tools that were seen as safe, structured and supportive. In addition, they valued the human support provided by the staff involved in the experiments – in particular the help they were given on using the tools and the encouragement and confidence-building offered.

Implications for the future

The implications of these conclusions for work in the field of supporting web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities going forward are as follows.

- The strongest key message from the above conclusions is that we don't know nearly enough about how gender is interweaved with cognitive disability and web accessibility. Most of the evidence base is in three different strands: cognitive disability, gender and digital accessibility - and these strands remain disconnected. There are some signs that some tools to support digital accessibility may be more effective for some men or some women – as evidenced by the handful of studies in the literature and our own research in the Co-Labs, reported on above – but these remain signs only. A more intensive, broader, more comprehensive and more systematic research effort is therefore needed to connect the dots between gender, cognitive disability and digital accessibility.
- Two areas are strong candidates for this increased research effort. First, on how 'intersectionality' works in this field. This needs to focus in more detail on how sex and gender combine with dynamics like ethnicity, economic situation, family background and presenting cognitive disability to shape access to, use of and benefits derived from digital tools and services. Second, research is needed on whether and in what ways particular tools to increase web accessibility work differently – and are more effective – for different sex and gender categorisations and typologies.
- Both areas imply more innovative research methodologies, methods and tools. In the case of 'intersectionality' research a more robust quantitative approach – involving larger population sizes across different categorisations and typologies – needs to be combined with more novel 'qualitative' and 'ethnographic' approaches. For example, LIVE IT has demonstrated that lifeworld analysis can be a powerful tool to reveal the specificity of the lived experience of cognitive disability through the prism of gender. Other tools – for example video ethnographies and blogs and, more broadly, participatory action research, could add significant value to lifeworld analysis and could have the added benefit of increasing participants' digital and media competences.
- In the case of research to establish whether and in what ways there is a connection between gender and tool efficacy, what's clear from LIVE IT's own research in its Co-Labs and Hackathons is that the complex potential inter-relationships between variables of interest in a typical experiment – for example presenting cognitive disability, experimental scenario and challenges covered, tool attributes, delivery mechanism and gender – are likely to test the limits of conventional models and methodologies – particularly in the typical case where experimental populations are small. We therefore need much bigger experimental populations and more sophisticated data capture and analysis tools – which brings into play the potential opportunities afforded by AI and machine learning. It's likely that only AI and

machine learning tools would have the capacity to identify and make sense of interactions and ‘causal relationships’ between tool attributes and user behaviours, so as to develop clusters of attribute-use behaviour combinations that demonstrate the best potential outcomes for inclusive web accessibility.

- In addition – as demonstrated by the literature reviews and our own experience of recruiting and engaging participants in Co-Labs and Hackathons – the voice of some representatives of the gender spectrum in research is almost silent. Although LIVE IT achieved a broad parity of sex representation in its activities, representation of people with cognitive disabilities who do not identify as binary was not achieved. People whose gender identity is non-binary need to be better represented in research going forward.
- Despite these clear research and evidence gaps, we do know something, from LIVE IT’s work, about how the interactions between cognitive disability, gender and digital accessibility are likely to pan out. For example, it seems clear that females bring with them less knowledge, skills, confidence and aspirations to the digital table. In the context of the here and now of designing and delivering effective policies, approaches and tools to support web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities this suggests some lessons that could be learned and applied. One is that active support for females needs to be built in across the whole IT design, delivery and implementation process. One keyway this could be done is to provide more extensive and comprehensive training in digital and media skills for females with cognitive disabilities. Another way is to increase the representation of females – and people who identify as non-binary – in positions of advocacy, leadership and decision-making across the board, from design and development in the IT sector, through standards bodies, to policy-making agencies.
- However, it’s clear from our results that there’s no quick fix. There’s no technological silver bullet that will at the touch of a screen icon magically transform the lives of female and non-binary people with cognitive disabilities. The roots of gender inequalities in access to, use of and benefits derived from digital tools and services for people with cognitive disabilities are embedded in the complex intersectionalities through which disability, gender, ethnicity, education and economic position mutually interact and reinforce inequalities. So, you start with revealing and interrogating the roots of structural inequalities and work upwards from there – for example, as noted above, recognising that women with cognitive disabilities are more likely to be less digitally competent, less confident about using technologies and more in need of support. This support needs to be provided across the spectrum, from improving digital and media skills training for females and non-binary people with cognitive disabilities, through embedding functionalities within tools that reflect their needs, to providing tailored support to help them utilise tools more effectively and in line with their needs.
- This last point brings into play a broader implication for web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities going forward. Given the complexity of intersectional dynamics and the variability of tool use and outcomes within the context of gender, it seems clear that the main lesson for tool designers, developers and service delivery entities is to support customisation and personalised use. All participants

involved in LIVE IT activities presented with highly variable and specific complex needs. These needs were not obviously mediated through gender – in the sense that females clearly showed a preference for particular tools and gained more benefit from using those tools, and vice versa. But gender brought a particular set of psychosocial and socio-cultural attributes to the table, centred around factors like previous digital experience, sense of self-efficacy and confidence, as well as particular levels of digital and media competences - and these attributes shaped their subsequent digital behaviours and perceptions of outcomes. This supports a need going forward for improving customisation and personalisation in design, development and implementation. On the one hand, this implies increased human support for users. On the other it implies a potential role in the future for machine-learning agents that learn from user behaviours in order to adapt tools more closely to user characteristics and needs.

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